

Species Diversity of Birds in Moeyungyi Wildlife Sanctuary, Bago Township

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Abstract

Moeyungyi is one of the Ramsar sites in Myanmar occupies 40 square miles and situated at near Pyinbongyi Village, Bago Region. The present work conducted to record bird species in the study area monthly. A total of 135 families representing 35 orders were recorded. Among them 82 species were terrestrial bird while 53 species shown that terrestrial birds including 89 were residents and 46 migrants. Diversity index of Shannon, $H'(3.39-4.19)$, Shannon Evenness, $E(0.88-0.95)$, Simpson's index, $1-D(0.96-2.0)$ and Simpson's dominance index, $1-D(0.02-0.04)$ had indicated that the bird species were diverse in Moeyungyi Wetland. Four species; *Mycteria leucocephala*, *Threskiornis melanoleucocephalus*, *Anhinga melanogaster* and *Ploceus hypoxanthus* were Nearly threatened (NT) while *Grus Antigone* (Sarus crane) was Endangered (EN) according to IUCN Red List.

Keywords: Ramsar, terrestrial, residents, Diversity index, Shannon, Simpson diverse, threatened, Endanger

Introduction

Birds also known as Aves, are a group of endothermic vertebrates characterized by feather, toothless beaked jaws, the laying of hard-shelled eggs, a high metabolic rate, a four-chambered heart, and a strong yet light weight skeleton. Birds live worldwide and range in size from the 5cm (2 in) bee humming bird to the 2-75 m (9ft) Ostrich. The current classification of living bird is roughly 24 orders, 187 families, over 2000 genera and over 9600 species (Hill, 2001). They rank as the world's most numerically successful class of tetrapods, with approximately ten living species, more than half of these being passerines, sometimes known as perching birds, seabirds and some water birds have evolved for swimming approximately 10000 known bird species about one fifth of which occur in South East Asia distributed among a vast range of habitats, from tropical rainforests to icy shores. (Birds of South East Asia, 2017)

In Southeast Asia, a total of 1500 bird species comprising will a large proportion endemic species are recorded. Exhibiting amazing behavioral and morphological diversity, birds play an essential role in the functioning of healthy ecosystems. Birdlife International is the Red List Authority for birds, coordinating the process of evaluating all of the world's bird species against the Red List categories and criteria in order to assess their extinction risk. Birdlife International (2015) has established that 1375 bird species (13 % of the total or roughly one in eight) are threatened with extinction

Myanmar supports a total of 1062 bird species, of which six are endemic, two have been introduced by humans and ten are rare or accidental. One species listed is extirpated in Myanmar and is not included in the species count. According the IUCN Red List Criteria, 6 species are Globally Threatened found in Myanmar. Eight of these species are Critically Endangered, twelve Endangered and twenty-six are Vulnerable species (VU).

According to the forest Department issued that under the wildlife Act 583/74, 50 bird species of 14 families are totally protected, 43 bird species of 18 families are protected and 13 species of eight families are seasonally protected (Ministry of Forestry, 1994).

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Diversity of avifauna is one of the most important ecological indicators to evaluate the quality of habitats of an ecosystem. Avifauna diversity has been decreasing due to habitat loss, habitat degradation and human disturbances. Destruction of natural habitats by cutting nesting trees and foraging plants are responsible for avifauna foraging habitat and nesting sites.

Wetlands are widely recognized as highly important ecosystem with diverse attributes including a distinctive avifauna. The water birds, both migratory and non-migratory are important components of the biodiversity of wetland throughout the world (Davidson and Deland, 2000). Moreover, wetlands are among the most biologically diverse and productive ecosystem on earth. (Karia, 2012)

The Moeyungyi Ramsar sites Wetland (40 square miles) is reservoir originally built in 1878 to provide in area for water transport and to relive downstream flooding. Overtime, the site become important for providing water to the surrounding rice paddy and as a fishing ground for the local community as well as being a wintering site for thousands of migratory waterbirds. Therefore, it is need to know not only the occurrence of terrestrial birds and water birds, but also their abundance and species diversity in this Wetland. The objectives of the study are

1. To record the bird species in the study area
2. To identify the avifauna and categorize the terrestrial bird and water birds
3. To analyze the diversity indexes of recorded bird species
4. To categorize the bird species regarding with their international conservation aspects

Materials and Methods

Study area

Moeyungyi wetland Sanctuary was chosen as study area which is 40 square miles(25600 acre). The present study was conducted in Moeyungyi wetland Sanctuary. It is located at 17° 30'N and 96° 32' E. It is far from 25km NE of Bago and 24km West of SittaungRiver. It is situated near Pynbongyi Village.

Study period

The study period lasted from January to December, 2018.

Data Collection

Monthly Data collection was based on point count method (Verner, 1985). Bird watching was conducted 6:00 - 8:00 AM, 15:00 – 17:00 PM. Birds were observed, recorded aided by binoculars and taking photographs. The identification method and taxonomic designation of bird species was followed after the method used by Robson (2017) and King and Diskinson (1975).

Data Analysis

Indices of Shannon diversity (H'), species richness (R), evenness (E_H) Simpson index (D) were used to access species diversity of terrestrial and water birds. All recorded numerical

data had been conducting with microsoft excel and represented as histograms. Recorded bird species were checked with international conservation standard such as Conservation of International Trade of Endangered Species (CITES) and International Union of Conservation of nature (IUCN).

Fig.1. Map of study area (Source: Google earth)

Results

A total of 135 species under 45 families representing 36 orders were recorded. Regarding with their habitat preference 82 species were terrestrial birds and 53 waterbirds species, indicating 46 migrants while 89 were residents.

Overall diversity of bird community during the study period. According to the Shannon Index (H') the high diversity value was (4.19) in terrestrial birds and (3.55) in water birds while (4.16) in resident birds and (3.39) in migratory birds. (fig.2)

With the respect of Simpson dominance index (D), the same index value (0.02) was found in both terrestrial birds and water birds, while (0.04) in migratory birds and (0.02) in resident bird(Fig.3).

According to the Simpson's index ($1-D$), the index value (1) was in terrestrial birds and (0.98) in waterbirds. The value also (0.96) in the resident birds and (0.96) in migratory birds.

Regarding with the assessment of Shannon evenness (E), the index value of terrestrial bird was (0.95) and (0.89) in water birds. Index value of resident bird was (0.98) and the value of migratory bird was (0.88).

Richness (S), high index value of resident birds was (8.42) and 4.18 in migratory birds. In terrestrial birds, the index value was (7.94) and (4.76) in that of water birds.

Habitat preference such as terrestrial birds, waterbirds and resident and migratory birds fluctuated by seasonal variation had been mentioned in Table 2. With the aspect of conservation recorded bird species had been checked with the standardized Criteria of IUCN and CITES.

Table1. Birds of Moeyungyi Wildlife Sanctuary Bago Region (January, 2018 to December, 2018)

No	Scientific Name	Common Name	Status	CITES	IUCN Lists;
1	<i>Dendrocygna bicolor</i>	Fulvous Whistling Duck	M		
2	<i>Dendrocygnajavanica</i>	Lesser Whistling-Duck	R		LC
3	<i>Sarkidiornismelanotos</i>	Comb Duck	R		
4	<i>Nettapuscoromandelianus</i>	Cotton Pygmy goose	R		LC
5	<i>Anaspoecilorhyncha</i>	Spot-billed Duck	M		LC
6	<i>Anasacutas</i>	Northern Pintail	M		LC
7	<i>Anasquerquedula</i>	Garganey	M		LC
8	<i>Tachybaptusruficollis</i>	Little Grebe	R		LC
9	<i>Mycteria leucocephala</i>	Painted Stork	M	I	NT
10	<i>Anastomusoscitans</i>	Asian Openbill	M	I	LC
11	<i>Leptoptilosjavanicus</i>	Lesser Adjutant	R		LC
12	<i>Leptoptilosdubius</i>	Greater Adjutant	R		LC
13	<i>Threskiornismelanocephalus</i>	Black-headed Ibis	M	I/II	NT
14	<i>Plegadisfalcinellus</i>	Glossy Ibis	M	I/II	LC
15	<i>Ixobrychussinensis</i>	Yellow Bittern	R	III	LC
16	<i>Ixobrychuseurhythmus</i>	Schrenck's Bittern	R		LC
17	<i>Ixobrychuscinnamomeus</i>	Cinnamon Bittern	R		LC
18	<i>Dupetorflavicollis</i>	Black Bittern	R		LC
19	<i>Nycticoraxnycticorax</i>	Black-crowned Night-Heron	R		LC
20	<i>Ardeolabacchus</i>	Chinese pond Heron	R		LC

Table 1.Continued

21	<i>Ardeolagrayi</i>	Indian pond Heron	R		LC
22	<i>Ardeacinerea</i>	Grey - Heron	R		LC
23	<i>Ardeapurplea</i>	Purple Heron	R		LC
24	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Cattle Egret	R		LC
25	<i>Casmerodiusalbus</i>	Great Egret	R	III	LC
26	<i>Mesophoyxintermedia</i>	Intermediate Egret	R		LC
27	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Little Egret	R		
28	<i>Phalacrocoraxniger</i>	Little Cormorant	R		LC
29	<i>Anhinga melanogaster</i>	Oriental Darter	R		NT
30	<i>Gallixrexcinerea</i>	Watercock	R		LC
31	<i>Porphyrioporphyrus</i>	Purple Swamphen	R		LC
32	<i>Gallinulachloropus</i>	Common Moorhen	M		LC
33	<i>Fulicaatra</i>	Common Coot	M		LC
34	<i>Grusantigone</i>	Sarus Crane	R	II	EN
35	<i>Numeniusarquata</i>	Eurasian Curlew	M		
36	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	Black winged Stilt	R		
37	<i>Vanellusindicus</i>	Red wattled Lapwing	R		LC
38	<i>Vanelluscinereus</i>	Grey headed Lapwing	R		LC
39	<i>Charadriusdubius</i>	Little Ringed Plover	M	II	LC
40	<i>Pluvialisfulva</i>	Pacific Golden Plover	M		LC

Table 1. Continued

41	<i>Hydrophasianuschirurgus</i>	Pheasant -tailed Jacana	R		LC
42	<i>Metopidiusindicus</i>	Bronze-winged Jacana	R		LC
43	<i>Gallinagogallinago</i>	Common Snipe	M	II	LC
44	<i>Actitishypoleucos</i>	Common Sandpiper	M	II	LC
45	<i>Tringaachropus</i>	Green Sandpiper	M	II	LC
46	<i>Tringaglareola</i>	Wood Sandpiper	M	II	LC
47	<i>Tringastagnatilis</i>	Marsh Sandpiper	M	II	LC
48	<i>Calidristemminckii</i>	Temminck's Stint	M		
49	<i>Glareolamaldivarum</i>	Oriental Pratincole	M		LC
50	<i>Chlidoniashybrida</i>	Whiskered Tern	M		LC
51	<i>Sternulaalbifrons</i>	Little Tern	M		LC
52	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	Common Tern	M		LC
53	<i>Pandionhaliaetus</i>	Osprey	M		LC
54	<i>Elanuscaeruleus</i>	Black-Shouldered Kite	R	I/II	LC
55	<i>Milvusmgrans</i>	Black-Kite	M	I/II	LC
56	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	Shikra	R	I/II	LC
57	<i>Circus spilonotus</i>	Eastern Marsh-Harrier	M	I/II	LC
58	<i>Circus aeruginnosus</i>	Western Marsh Harrier	M	I/II	LC
59	<i>Circus melanoleucos</i>	Pied Harrier	M	I/II	LC
60	<i>Circus cyaneus</i>	Hen Harrier	M	I/II	LC

Table 1. Continued

61	<i>Columba livia</i>	Rock Pigeon	R		LC
62	<i>Streptopelia tranquebarica</i>	Red Collared Dove	R	III	LC
63	<i>Streptopelia chinensis</i>	Spotted Dove	R	III	LC
64	<i>Streptopelia orientalis</i>	Oriental turtle Dove			
65	<i>Cacomantis merulinus</i>	Plaintive Cuckoo	R		LC
66	<i>Eudynamis scolopacea</i>	Asian Koel	R		LC
67	<i>Tyto alba</i>	Common Barn-Owl	R	I/II	LC
68	<i>Octus sunia</i>	Oriental Scops Owl	R		LC
69	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	Greater Coucal	R		LC
70	<i>Centropus bengalensis</i>	Lesser Coucal	R		LC
71	<i>Cypsiurus balasienis</i>	Asian palm- Swift	R		LC
72	<i>Collocalia brevirostris</i>	Himalayan Swiftlet	R		
73	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	White - throated Kingfisher	R		LC
74	<i>Halcyon pileata</i>	Black-capped Kingfisher	M		LC
75	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	Common Kingfisher	R		LC
76	<i>Lanius collurioides</i>	Burmese Shrike	R		LC
77	<i>Lanius schach</i>	Long- tailed Shrike	R		LC
78	<i>Lanius cristatus</i>	Brown Shrike	M		LC
79	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	Green Bee- eater	R		LC
80	<i>Merops philippinus</i>	Blue -tailed Bee eater	R		LC
81	<i>Upupa epops</i>	Common Hoopoe	M		LC
82	<i>Dicrurus paradiseus</i>	Greater racket-tailed Drongo	R		LC
83	<i>Dicrurus remifer</i>	Lesser racket-tailed Drongo	R		LC
84	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>	Black Drongo	M		LC
85	<i>Dicrurus annectans</i>	Crow-billed Drongo			LC

Table 1. Continued

86	<i>Aegithinatiphia</i>	Common Iora	R		LC
87	<i>Orthotomussutorius</i>	Common Tailorbird	R		LC
88	<i>Corvussplendens</i>	House Crow	R		LC
89	<i>Corvusmacrorynchos</i>	Large billed Drongo			
90	<i>Coraciasbenghalensis</i>	Indian Roller	R		LC
91	<i>Acridotheresfuscus</i>	Jungle Myna	R		LC
92	<i>Graculareligiosa</i>	Hill myna	R		LC
93	<i>Acridotherestrictis</i>	Common Myna	R		LC
94	<i>Sturnus contra</i>	Asian Pied Starling	R		LC
95	<i>Sturnusmalabaricus</i>	Chestnut-tailed Starling	R		LC
96	<i>Sturnussinensis</i>	Whited Shoulder Starling	R		LC
97	<i>Sturnusburmannicus</i>	Vinous-Breasted Starling	R		LC
98	<i>Lusciniasvecica</i>	Bluethroat	M		LC
99	<i>Saxicolamaura</i>	Siberian Stonechat	R		LC
100	<i>Saxicolaleucura</i>	White-tailed Stonechat	R		
101	<i>Saxicolacaprata</i>	Pied Bushchat	R		LC
102	<i>Copsychussaularis</i>	Oriental Magpie Robin	R		LC
103	<i>Copsychusmalabaricus</i>	White rumped Shama	R		LC
104	<i>Megalaimahaemacephala</i>	Coppersmith Barbet	R		LC
105	<i>Megalaimalineata</i>	Lineated Barbet	R		LC
106	<i>Alaudagulgula</i>	Oriental Skylark	M		LC
107	<i>Pycnonotusblanfordi</i>	Streak-eared Bulbul	R		LC
108	<i>Pycnonotusjocosus</i>	Red-Whiskered Bulbul	R		LC
109	<i>Pycononotuscafer</i>	Red- Vented Bulbul	R		LC
110	<i>Pycononotusatriceps</i>	Black-headed Bulbul	R		LC

Table 1. Continued

111	<i>Pyconotus flaviventris</i>	Black-crested Bulbul	R		LC
112	<i>Turdoides guaris</i>	White-throated Bulbul	R		LC
113	<i>Chrysommasinense</i>	Yellow-eyed Babbler	R		
114	<i>Phylloscopus fuscatus</i>	Dusky Warbler	M		LC
115	<i>Acrocephalus agricola</i>	Paddy-field Warbler	M		
116	<i>Acrocephalus orientalis</i>	Oriental Reed Warbler	M		LC
117	<i>Megalurus palustris</i>	Striated Grassbird	R		LC
118	<i>Cisticola juncidis</i>	Zitting Cisticola	R		LC
119	<i>Prinia inornata</i>	Plain Prinia	R		LC
120	<i>Lonchura striata</i>	White-rumped Munia	R		LC
121	<i>Lonchura punctulata</i>	Scaly-breasted Munia	R		LC
122	<i>Lonchura maja</i>	Black-headed Munia	R		LC
123	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	Baya Weaver	R	III	LC
124	<i>Ploceus hypoxanthus</i>	Asian Golden Weaver	R		NT
125	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House Sparrow	R		LC
126	<i>Passer montanus</i>	Eurasian Tree-Sparrow	R		LC
127	<i>Dicaeum cruentatum</i>	Scarlet-backed Flowerpecker	R		LC
128	<i>Ficedula parva</i>	Red-throated Flycatcher	M		LC
129	<i>Jynx torquilla</i>	Eurasian Wryneck	M		LC
130	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	White Wagtail	M		LC
131	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	Yellow Wagtail	M		LC
132	<i>Motacilla citreola</i>	Citrine Wagtail	M		LC
133	<i>Anthus cervinus</i>	Red-throated Pipit	M		LC
134	<i>Anthus rufulus</i>	Paddy field Pipit	R		LC
135	<i>Anthus richardi</i>	Olive-backed Pipit	R		LC

Resident birds (R), Migratory birds (M)

Fig.2. Shannon index (H') different measure of bird diversity

Fig.3. Simpson's dominance index (different measure of bird diversity)

Fig.4. Simpson's index (1-D) different measure of bird diversity

Fig.5. Shannon evenness (E) different measure of bird diversity

Fig.6. Richness (S) different measure of bird diversity

Discussion

A total of 82 terrestrial birds and 53 water bird species were recorded during the study period. Among them birds, 89 resident and 46 were migratory birds. This record is the highest number of species diversity compared with 52 species mentioned by ThetThetMyintet. Al (2000 – 2009) and 300 species recorded by Phyo Phyo Kyi, 2015(data unpublished) in the somestudy area, Moeyungyi Wetland. According to the Myanmar Wildlife Protection Law (1994), a total of 135 species were recorded as 43 protected species, 13 seasonally protected species and 15 as totally protected species.

The species, *Mycteria leucocephala* (Painted Stork), *Threskiornis melanocephalus* (Black-headed Ibis), *Anhinga melanogaster* (Oriental Darter), *Ploceushypoxanthus* (Asian Golden Weaver) were recorded as “Near Threatened species (NT)”. The species, *Grus antigone* (Sarus Crane) as “Endangered species” (EN) regarding with IUCN.

Shannon index (H') shown that the terrestrial birds were high diversity values (4.19) compared with that of (3.55) in water birds while (4.16) in residence birds was more diverse than (3.39) in migratory birds (Fig.A).

With the aspect of Simpson dominance index (D), the same index values (0.02) in terrestrial birds and water birds while 0.04 in migratory birds that of resident birds was also 0.02 (Fig.B).

Simpson's index (1-D) also shown that the index value (1) in terrestrial birds compared with that of (0.98) in water birds. The value was also (0.98) in the residence birds and that of migratory birds shown (0.96) (Fig.C).

According to the assessment of Shannon evenness (E), the index value of terrestrial bird shown (0.95) compared with that of (0.89) in aquatic birds. Index values of (0.98) of residence birds occurred and that of migratory birds was 0.88 (Fig D).

The higher index value of resident birds (8.42) represent more diversity than migratory birds (4.18). The higher index value of terrestrial birds (7.94) represent more diversity than water birds (4.76)

The relative abundance of *Prinia inornata* (Plain Prinia) occurred 3.40 % that was the highest among terrestrial birds that of 7.99 % in *Sternula albifrons* (Little Tern) was the highest among water birds.

Prinia inornata (Plain Prinia) occurred 3.40 % that was the highest among terrestrial birds that of 7.99 % in *Sternula albifrons* (Little Tern) was the highest among water birds.

Dendrocygna javanica (Lesser Whistling Duck) occurred 8.08 % that was the highest among resident birds that of 6.72 % in *Sterna hirundo* (Common Tern) was the highest among migratory birds

As a conclusion, the positive values of diversity indexes and relative abundance of avian fauna for different measures such as terrestrial birds, aquatic birds, resident birds and aquatic birds shown that the study area is sustainable habitat for the year round study of avian fauna. Diversity index of Shannon and Simpson were positive that shows that Moeyungyi Wetland is habitat heterogeneity providing rich in food receive for avifauna. Bird watching may be the whether aspect regarding with attraction by concerning the sustainable ecosystem of Moeyungyi Wetland.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to Rector, Dr Aye Aye Tun and Pro-Rector, Dr Yin Yin Than for their constant encouragement and permission to conduct this research. Special thanks go to Daw Thin Thin Yu, Park Warden of Moeyungyi Wildlife Sanctuary, Daw Nilar Pwint, Range officer of Inndawgyi Wildlife Sanctuary and U Kyaw Thu, Administrator of Pinyinbongyi Village, Bago Township, Bago Region.

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